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Timing of Autism Recognition Among Israeli Children: Community and Socioeconomic Factors

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Timing of Autism Recognition Among Israeli Children: Community and Socioeconomic Factors

Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) represents one of the most significant shifts in neurodevelopmental diagnosis patterns globally over the past two decades. While global prevalence is currently estimated at 1 in 100 children (Zeidan et al., 2022), individual countries report even higher rates. In the United States, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) surveillance data show an increase from 1 in 150 children in 2000 (equivalent to 7 out of every 1,000) to 1 in 31 children (32 out of every 1,000) in 2022 (Shaw et al., 2025), while the United Kingdom reports current prevalence rates of approximately 1–2% (Roman-Urrestarazu et al., 2021).

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In Israel, the ASD diagnosis rate increased from 4.5 per 1,000 among individuals born in 2000 to 22.2 per 1,000 among those born in 2018 (Central Bureau of Statistics [CBS], 2024). Recent analyses have documented similarly dramatic increases, with ASD prevalence doubling between 2017 and 2021 alone (Dinstein et al., 2024). These trends are mirrored in the Israeli school system (Figure 1), where students in dedicated special education classrooms for ASD have grown from 1,905 students (0.11% of the student body) in 2004/05 to 35,787 students (1.4% of the student body) in 2024/25.¹ When including special education students integrated in general education classrooms, ASD rates rose from 1.1% in 2020/21 to 1.8% in 2023/24, with current estimates suggesting that approximately 2% of the student body has a primary ASD diagnosis.² This acceleration is even more pronounced in preschool settings, where ASD rates nearly doubled from 1.3% to 2.4% over this same period. Over the full 20-year span from 2004/05 to 2024/25, this represents growth from approximately 1 per 1,000 students to 20 per 1,000 students, with a notable shift from gradual increases over the first decade to exponential acceleration in recent years.

1 Calculated using the Ministry of Education's Wide Perspective (מבט רחב), a government-maintained database that provides detailed information on student enrollment in educational institutions in Israel. It offers data on student numbers per institution, categorized by location, supervision, sector, and type (general or special education).

2 Data for 2020/21–2023/24 were provided directly by the Ministry of Education and include special education students receiving inclusion services in general education classrooms.

Figure 1. Number of students (preschool through Grade 12) with ASD in the school system

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Education

Changes in diagnostic criteria contributed to the increase worldwide (Maenner et al., 2023). The implementation of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), in 2013 marked a significant shift in ASD diagnosis criteria, consolidating previously separate autism-related diagnoses, including what was formerly known as Asperger's syndrome, into a single umbrella diagnosis of ASD (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Although researchers originally predicted that the diagnostic changes would be restrictive and lead to a reduction in ASD diagnoses (Kulage et al., 2014; Maenner et al., 2014), the period following DSM-5 implementation has coincided with continued growth in ASD diagnoses, suggesting that the unified spectrum framework contributed to the observed increase, with effects likely building over time, as the changes diffused through clinical practice.

Beyond diagnostic criteria changes, several additional factors likely contributed to the rising prevalence of ASD diagnoses. Increased awareness among parents, educators, and healthcare providers has led to better recognition of autism symptoms and earlier screening practices. The current best practice emphasizes identification by 2–3 years of age rather than later in childhood,

thereby capturing cases that might previously have been missed or identified much later (Guthrie et al., 2019; Hyman et al., 2020). Additionally, reduced stigma surrounding neurodevelopmental conditions has made families more willing to seek diagnosis and support, with research demonstrating a consistent inverse relationship between stigma and help-seeking behavior across mental health conditions (Clement et al., 2015). These shifts in awareness and attitudes make Israel's comprehensive financial and educational support services for children with ASD, including disability allowances ranging from NIS 3,700 to NIS 8,800 monthly payments, particularly powerful incentives for families seeking formal diagnosis (Amit et al., 2024). Some researchers also point to environmental factors, such as advanced parental age and various prenatal and perinatal risk factors (Emberti Gialloreti et al., 2019). These converging factors: diagnostic framework changes, heightened awareness, available services, and potential environmental influences, contribute to the substantial growth in ASD diagnoses.

While these factors have contributed to the spike in ASD diagnoses, their impact has been far from uniform across segments of Israeli society, with higher ASD rates concentrated among higher socioeconomic groups. Previous nationwide research examining children born between 2000–2012 documented consistently higher ASD incidence rates among higher-SES groups (Segev et al., 2019). More recent data from both the CBS and the Ministry of Education confirm these socioeconomic inequalities and reveal higher ASD prevalence among children from higher socioeconomic status (SES) areas than those from lower SES brackets. Among cohorts born 2013 and 2018, diagnosis rates peaked at 30 per 1,000 in SES clusters 7–8, compared to 15 per 1,000 for children from the lowest SES areas (CBS, 2024). This pattern is mirrored in the school system, where the general student population is composed of 58% from SES clusters 5–10, compared with 76% among students with a primary ASD diagnosis, indicating a greater share of high socioeconomic groups in the ASD population (Silverman & Blass, 2025). Income-based differences, while more modest, have also persisted consistently across time periods, with children from higher-income families showing consistently higher rates of ASD diagnosis (CBS, 2024).

Despite being underrepresented in ASD diagnoses, children from low SES households are at greater risk for language and communication delays. Our previous study using Tipat Halav data found a strong relationship between language milestone attainment and maternal education, which is a key indicator

of family SES (Akiva et al., 2024). Lower maternal education was consistently linked to higher rates of delayed language milestone attainment. While delayed milestone attainment is not itself a diagnostic tool, it indicates an increased likelihood of developmental delay or disability. Research has demonstrated that language delays serve as important early indicators of subsequent ASD diagnosis in public healthcare settings (Nitzan et al., 2023).

These findings reveal a striking paradox: children from low SES homes face higher risks for the very language and communication difficulties that characterize ASD, yet remain significantly underrepresented in this rapidly expanding diagnostic category. This paradox is further complicated by a range of factors that vary across Israel's diverse population. Multiple factors — including healthcare-seeking approaches, accessibility to health services, and attitudes toward developmental evaluations — may contribute to lower consultation rates in certain communities, including Haredi, Bedouin, and Arab populations. These patterns, combined with socioeconomic factors and differential access to diagnostic services, create complex challenges that compound inequalities in ASD diagnosis rates in Israel (Koller et al., 2021). The result is a classic Matthew effect: despite Israel's substantial ASD support benefits, these resources are paradoxically more readily accessed by families with greater resources and system navigation skills, further widening rather than closing diagnostic gaps (Pavolini & Lancker, 2019).

The documented differences in ASD diagnosis rates by SES raise an important question: Do these gaps also affect when children receive their diagnoses and subsequent social benefits? We hypothesize that advances in early diagnostic tools have not benefited all groups equally. Group-specific factors and differences in families' ability to navigate diagnostic systems may cause systematic delays for some populations (Koller et al., 2021). This is critical because, as noted, best practices recommend diagnosis by ages 2–3 years for optimal intervention outcomes (Dawson et al., 2010; Hyman et al., 2020; Zwaigenbaum et al., 2015); delayed diagnosis reduces the clinical effectiveness of such interventions. Therefore, this study examines how SES and population group relate to diagnosis timing, helping us understand what drives these patterns.

Data and statistical methods

Data sources

This study combines comprehensive datasets from Israel's Tipat Halav well-baby clinic system and the National Insurance Institute (NII) to examine the relationship between local SES, population group, and the timing of ASD diagnosis. The Tipat Halav system offers universal preventive healthcare services to Israeli children from birth through age six. The Tipat Halav dataset from the Ministry of Health includes longitudinal developmental assessments and family demographic information for approximately 70% of the national population. The NII maintains comprehensive records of all disability allowances, including detailed eligibility information. In addition, the geographic statistical area of residence was linked against external tables from CBS and the data organization Points (Points, 2019), which provide sociodemographic variables per area. All of the data used for this study was fully anonymized and was available through Timna, the Ministry of Health's big data platform.

Study population

The analysis included all children born on or after January 1, 2014, who had been assessed at least once at Tipat Halav and were eligible for an NII allowance due to ASD as of March 19, 2023. Children included in the analysis had records in both systems, allowing us to combine early developmental data from Tipat Halav with information on ASD allowances from the NII.

Outcome variable

The dependent variable was the child's earliest age of eligibility for an ASD allowance, calculated from the child's date of birth to their first approval date. While eligibility for an allowance serves as a proxy for formal diagnosis timing — as clinical diagnosis is required for allowance applications — this measure provides a standardized, population-wide indicator of when ASD recognition occurred within the healthcare system.

Study variables

Our data allow us to characterize each child using multiple variables including maternal demographics, birth-related measures, and longitudinal developmental assessments. Table 1 presents the complete list of variables by data source.

Table 1. Variables by data source

Data source	Variable category	Specific variables	Values
Tipat Halav	Maternal demographics	Employment status	employed, unemployed, student
		Marital status	married, single, divorced, other
		Population group	Jewish, non-Jewish (Muslim Arab, Christian Arab, Druze, Bedouin, other)
		Maternal age at birth	under 20, 21–40, over 40
		Mother's country of birth	Israel, FSU, Ethiopia, other
	Birth characteristics	Gestational age at birth	under 28 weeks, 28–31 weeks, 32–36 weeks, over 37 weeks
		Birthweight	under 2.5 kg, 2.5–4 kg, over 4 kg
		Apgar scores	under 8 or over 8, 1 and 5 minutes after birth
		Delivery type	vaginal, assisted delivery, Cesarean section
	Child characteristics	Sex	male, female
		Developmental milestone scores	see below
	Geographic	Statistical area of residence	1,553 areas
	National Insurance Institute	Outcome variable	Age at eligibility for ASD allowance
External sources	Family SES	Income level, employment history	
	Area-level variables	Socioeconomic cluster	1–10
		Haredi population proportion	5-level measure: none; low; medium; high; very high. Grouped as non-Haredi areas (none, low), Haredi areas (mixed, high, very high)

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

The socioeconomic cluster categorizes communities into 10 SES levels (1 = lowest, 10 = highest) based on income, education, and employment. We grouped these into five categories (1–2, 3–4, 5–6, 7–8, 9–10) for meaningful analysis. Consistent with population data, only 5% of the children are in the highest bracket (9–10), limiting trend visibility, therefore 7–8 serves as a better reference for high SES. Individual family religious identity within the Jewish population (e.g., secular, national religious, Haredi) was not available in our dataset. The Haredi population proportion is a neighborhood-level variable that allows us to examine how ASD diagnosis patterns may differ between segments of Israeli society in the absence of family-level religious characteristics. Areas classified as *non-Haredi* include neighborhoods with none, low or mixed levels of Haredi residents and may include secular, national religious, traditional, and other Jewish populations, as well as mixed Jewish-Arab neighborhoods.

Statistical analysis

We employed a two-step analytical approach. First, we calculated descriptive statistics and examined basic patterns of eligibility age, stratified by key variables such as socioeconomic cluster and proportion of Haredi population in the area of residency. Second, we constructed mixed-effects linear regression models to assess the relationship between sociodemographic variables and age of eligibility for an allowance.

The mixed-effects models included family-level demographic predictors and child-level birth- and development-related predictors as control variables (Appendix Table 1). Random intercepts were included for the 1,553 geographic statistical areas to account for unobserved area-level factors, while area-level socioeconomic predictors were modeled as fixed effects. Geographic variables were based on information from Points and the CBS, including local socioeconomic clusters and proportion of Haredi population in each area (categorized as none, low, medium, high, or very high).

In a secondary analysis, we examined additional control variables and specific subgroups:

1. We controlled for children's developmental status by including their peak developmental concern scores (high scores indicating high developmental concern) across all visits from birth to age 3, calculated for milestone assessments in language, social, gross motor, and fine motor domains (Bilu et al., 2023).

2. We constructed separate models for subgroups of children, based on their population group (Jewish/non-Jewish) and, for Jewish children, the proportion of Haredi population in their residential neighborhoods.

Missing values in categorical variables were handled as a distinct category. All analyses were performed using Python version 3.9 and R version 4.2 (lme4 package version 1.1–31).

Results

Descriptive statistics

The cohort included 16,993 children who had both Tipat Halav records and NII eligibility for ASD allowances. This group comprises 69.6% of all children with ASD-related allowances in the NII dataset, consistent with the nationwide proportion of children represented in the Tipat Halav dataset. The study population was predominantly male (76%) and Jewish (73%), with additional representation from Muslim Arab (8.8%), Christian Arab (0.7%), Druze (0.5%), and Bedouin (0.4%) communities (Appendix Table 1). The average age of eligibility for ASD allowances was 3.0 years (standard deviation 1.7 years), with the middle 50% of children becoming eligible between ages 1.8 and 4.0 years (Appendix Table 1). Eligibility timing varied by demographics: females became eligible slightly later than males (3.2 versus 3.0 years), and Jewish children showed later eligibility compared to Muslim Arabs (3.0 versus 2.8 years).

Figure 2. Age of eligibility for ASD allowance by SES cluster (unadjusted)

Notes: The boxes show the median line, as well as the first and third quartiles. The whiskers extend to the values within 1.5 IQR. Black dots represent the mean values.

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Initial analysis (Figure 2) revealed apparent socioeconomic gradients in eligibility timing, with children from the lowest SES clusters (1–2) becoming eligible on average 1.3 years later than middle-upper (5–8) SES groups (4.0 versus 2.7 years). When examined by population group, these socioeconomic differences were concentrated exclusively among Jewish children, who showed a pronounced stepwise pattern from 4.0 years in the lowest clusters (1–2) to 2.7 years in middle-upper (5–8) clusters, while non-Jewish children showed consistently early eligibility (2.4–2.9 years) across all SES levels. However, after stratifying for neighborhood religious composition, the SES effects among non-Haredi Jewish children disappeared entirely (Figure 3). Instead, the disparities remained among residents in predominantly Haredi neighborhoods, where children became eligible substantially later (4.7 years) than did Jewish children in non-Haredi neighborhoods who showed consistently earlier eligibility age (2.7 years) across all SES levels.

Figure 3. Age of eligibility for ASD allowance by SES cluster for Jewish children residing in Haredi versus non-Haredi areas, and for non-Jewish children

Note: The numbers above the plots indicate the number of children in each group.

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Multivariate analysis results

Mixed-effects regression models (Appendix Table 2) confirmed the patterns observed in the descriptive statistics analysis. Higher socioeconomic clusters (5–6 and 7–8) remained strongly associated with earlier eligibility timing compared to the lowest socioeconomic group (clusters 1–2). This association persisted even after controlling for children's developmental status. Additional factors associated with earlier diagnosis included single motherhood and mothers from Ethiopia or the former Soviet Union (FSU). Conversely, factors associated with later diagnosis included residence in areas with medium, high, and very high proportions of Haredi population (relative to non-Haredi areas) and young maternal age (20 years or younger). The robustness of these findings across different analytical approaches strengthens confidence in the observed patterns of diagnostic inequalities and their implications for policy intervention.

Examination of the group-specific models (Appendix Table 3) confirms that the association between eligibility age and socioeconomic cluster is mostly apparent in the population residing in Haredi neighborhoods, while for Jewish children residing in non-Haredi areas, as well as for non-Jewish children, no such association exists. This result is confirmed by a supplementary model (Appendix Table 4), which included only non-Haredi population (both Jewish and non-Jewish). Using this model, it is also observed that Muslim Arabs and children without recorded nationality (who are more likely to be non-Jewish) obtained eligibility at slightly older ages compared to Jewish children (3 months for Muslim Arabs, and 5.5 months for children with missing records), and these associations persist when controlling for the children's developmental status (Model 2).

Discussion

This study reveals substantial differences in the timing of ASD recognition across Israel's diverse population, with the largest gaps driven by the share of Haredim in a neighborhood rather than socioeconomic factors. Surface-level patterns suggested that socioeconomic factors drive diagnostic timing differences, showing a 1.3-year gap in ASD eligibility between lowest and mid-high SES groups, which persists when controlling for demographic and obstetrics factors. However, controlling for neighborhood composition revealed that residing in predominantly Haredi areas is the primary variable underlying these inequalities, eliminating socioeconomic effects entirely. Children from

predominantly Haredi neighborhoods get ASD recognition on average two years later than their peers from non-Haredi neighborhoods. Non-Jewish populations show different patterns: they have significantly lower ASD diagnosis rates, and among those who are diagnosed, eligibility timing shows no relationship with SES. All the study findings persist even after accounting for children's actual developmental ability, indicating that the differences likely stem from systemic barriers to recognition and diagnosis rather than differences in underlying developmental difficulties.

Among non-Jewish families, the consistently early and uniform eligibility ages, combined with their lower rates of ASD recognition, may reflect several factors: limited socioeconomic variability within these communities, barriers to disability recognition that can be labeled as *cultural* (e.g., seeing disability differently, stigmatizing it differently); or a pattern where primarily children with more severe, readily apparent forms of autism receive evaluation in these communities. Among Jewish families in non-Haredi neighborhoods, the findings revealed a pattern that defied our initial expectations. We expected to find socioeconomic effects on diagnostic timing, however, these communities showed remarkable equality in timing across SES levels. This, along with lower prevalence rates among low SES communities, suggests that the primary barrier is not differential access to timely diagnosis, but rather differences in who seeks evaluation in the first place, which is consistent with the SES prevalence patterns documented in the introduction, and indicates a recognition gap rather than a timing gap.

In contrast, residents of Haredi neighborhoods reveal a more complex pattern of barriers, with both timing delays and prevalence gaps. Children in these communities become eligible two years later than those in non-Haredi areas (4.7 versus 2.7 years). This pattern creates compounding disadvantages: not only are children in Haredi communities less likely to be diagnosed with autism, but those who are identified receive recognition years after the critical early intervention window, when interventions are less effective and developmental trajectories more difficult to alter.

These findings raise important questions about autism recognition in Israel. With ASD diagnoses now affecting approximately 2% of the student body and continuing to rise, our results show that the majority of these students come from more advantaged groups in society. This contrasts with international patterns observed across high-income countries, where autism diagnoses were

initially concentrated among higher socioeconomic and majority populations, but over time reached previously underserved communities as awareness and access improved (Maenner, 2023; Russell et al., 2022; Zeidan et al., 2022). For example, in the United States the prevalence gap not only closed but reversed, with Black 8-year-old children showing higher autism identification rates than White children in 2020 (Maenner, 2023). In Israel, however, we did not find this pattern of expanding identification among low SES and minority populations. Diagnoses remain concentrated in higher-SES, non-Haredi Jewish communities, while other groups remain largely outside the diagnostic system despite evidence of developmental risk (Akiva et al., 2024). The evidence points toward systematic under-recognition in specific populations, with the policy challenge to ensure that early intervention resources reach all children who could benefit.

Policy options

The disparities documented in this study demand urgent policy interventions to ensure equitable access to early ASD recognition and support. Our findings point to two complementary approaches: universal screening mechanisms and targeted support systems for underserved populations.

Implementing universal ASD screening in Tipat Halav clinics

The most promising avenue for addressing these inequalities lies in leveraging Israel's existing maternal child health infrastructure. Our previous research using this same dataset demonstrates that ASD can be accurately predicted using routine developmental milestone data already collected in Tipat Halav clinics (Amit et al., 2024). This predictive model achieved performance superior to the Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers (M-CHAT) when applied at 18 to 24 months of age, which is ideal timing for early diagnosis. Critically, this approach requires no additional infrastructure investment, uses milestones already routinely assessed, and can be seamlessly integrated into existing clinical workflows. Most importantly, the model performs equally well across different population groups and socioeconomic levels, providing objective, standardized screening that is independent of family advocacy skills or bureaucratic navigation capacity. This represents yet another example of Tipat Halav's potential as a powerful equalizing force in Israeli healthcare,

reaching nearly all families regardless of socioeconomic status and providing universal access to developmental surveillance that can identify children at risk before differences in family resources create barriers to recognition and intervention.

Targeted interventions for underserved populations

Despite its many advantages, universal screening alone cannot address the complex barriers facing low-SES and diverse families, since identifying children at risk for ASD does not guarantee they will receive formal diagnosis or access services. Our findings that timing inequalities persist even after controlling for developmental ability indicate that systemic barriers, rather than clinical factors, drive these inequities. Targeted interventions should include proactive case management for families from underserved communities, with dedicated coordinators guiding them through the entire process from screening to service access. Community-based outreach programs could deploy screening and support services directly in neighborhoods with high concentrations of Haredi residents or low-SES families. Additional policy interventions should include cultural sensitivity training for providers, community-appropriate educational materials, and liaison programs that reduce barriers within existing community frameworks.

Conclusion

ASD diagnoses continue to rise, now affecting 2% of Israel's student body and driving increased special education placements. The cost of inaction extends far beyond individual families. Early intervention produces the best outcomes when initiated before age three, making these timing delays both harmful and economically inefficient.

This study reveals that Haredi community composition, more than SES, drives the largest disparities in autism recognition timing in Israel. Children from predominantly Haredi neighborhoods become eligible for ASD allowances two years later, on average, than their peers. This delay occurs during the critical early intervention window, when treatment is most effective. Our findings also reinforce previous observations: ASD support is predominantly found among Jewish children from non-Haredi neighborhoods and mid-to-high SES families.

Reducing the inequalities can be achieved by leveraging Israel's existing strengths while overcoming specific barriers. Universal ASD screening through Tipat Halav clinics could identify at-risk children earlier without requiring new infrastructure, using developmental milestone data already collected. For Haredi and other underserved communities, targeted outreach programs and culturally sensitive navigation support could bridge the gap between identification and services.

Israel has the infrastructure and expertise to ensure that all children receive timely autism recognition and support — regardless of family and community background. We need systemic changes to ensure early intervention reaches those who need it most, not just those best positioned to navigate complex bureaucratic systems.

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Appendix

Appendix Table 1. Population characteristics by ASD status

	No ASD N (%)	ASD N (%)	Diagnosis age (years)	
			Mean ± SD	Median (IQR)
TOTAL	1,040,452 (98.4)	16,993 (1.6)	3 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4)
Sex				
Female	509,287 (49.9)	4,096 (24.0)	3.2 ± 1.8	2.7 (1.8, 4.3)
Male	531,165 (51.1)	12,907 (76.0)	3 ± 1.6	2.5 (1.8, 3.9)
Population sector				
Jewish	688,964 (66.2)	12,446 (73.2)	3 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.7, 4)
Muslim Arab	204,205 (19.6)	1,495 (8.8)	2.8 ± 1.4	2.5 (1.9, 3.4)
Christian Arab	13,664 (1.3)	115 (0.7)	2.8 ± 1.2	2.6 (2, 3.4)
Druze	15,350 (1.5)	80 (0.5)	3 ± 1.5	2.7 (1.9, 3.4)
Muslim Bedouin	21,741 (2.1)	61 (0.4)	2.2 ± 0.7	2.2 (1.5, 2.7)
Other	18,771 (1.8)	863 (5.1)	2.6 ± 1.4	2.2 (1.7, 3.1)
Missing	77,757 (7.5)	1,933 (11.4)	3.4 ± 1.7	3 (2, 4.7)
Maternal country of origin				
Israel	810,430 (77.9)	11,402 (67.1)	3.2 ± 1.7	2.7 (1.8, 4.3)
FSU	56,259 (5.4)	2,114 (12.4)	2.5 ± 1.3	2.2 (1.6, 3.1)
Ethiopia	14,960 (1.4)	564 (3.3)	2.6 ± 1.1	2.3 (1.9, 3)
Other	39,319 (3.8)	556 (3.3)	3.2 ± 1.7	2.7 (1.8, 4.4)
Missing	119,484 (11.5)	2,357 (13.9)	3 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 3.8)
Maternal education				
Primary	19,477 (1.9)	270 (1.6)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.9, 3.7)
High school	26,0381 (25.0)	4,907 (28.9)	3 ± 1.7	2.5 (1.7, 3.8)
Tertiary education	108,776 (10.5)	1,451 (8.5)	3.3 ± 1.8	2.9 (1.9, 4.6)
Academic	298,623 (28.7)	4,229 (24.9)	2.9 ± 1.5	2.5 (1.7, 3.7)
Missing	353,195 (33.9)	6,136 (36.1)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.7 (1.8, 4.3)
Maternal marital status				
Married	863,649 (83.0)	12,722 (74.9)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4.2)
Divorced	10,027 (1.0)	448 (2.6)	2.7 ± 1.4	2.2 (1.6, 3.2)
Single	32,660 (3.1)	1,239 (7.3)	2.5 ± 1.3	2.2 (1.6, 3)
Widow	505 (0.0)	13 (0.1)	2.7 ± 1.2	2.2 (2.1, 3)
Other	10,859 (1.0)	307 (1.8)	2.8 ± 1.5	2.4 (1.8, 3.5)
Missing	122,752 (11.8)	2,264 (13.3)	3 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 3.9)

Appendix Table 1 (continued). Population characteristics by ASD status

	No ASD N (%)	ASD N (%)	Diagnosis age (years)	
			Mean ± SD	Median (IQR)
Maternal employment				
Employed	463,559 (44.6)	7,423 (43.7)	3 ± 1.6	2.5 (1.7, 3.8)
Unemployed	197,509 (19.0)	2,977 (17.5)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4.2)
Student	41,909 (4.0)	395 (2.3)	3 ± 1.6	2.4 (1.8, 3.9)
Missing	337,475 (32.4)	6,198 (36.5)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.7 (1.8, 4.1)
Maternal age at birth				
Under 20	2,805 (0.3)	46 (0.3)	3.8 ± 2	3.6 (1.8, 5.9)
21–40	855,975 (82.3)	13,130 (77.3)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4.1)
Over 40	113,973 (11.0)	2,454 (14.4)	2.8 ± 1.4	2.4 (1.7, 3.5)
Missing	67,699 (6.5)	1,363 (8.0)	3.1 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 4)
Delivery type				
Spontaneous	745,530 (71.7)	10,483 (61.7)	3.1 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 4.1)
Cesarean section	180,333 (17.3)	4,277 (25.2)	2.6 ± 1.4	2.2 (1.6, 3.2)
Instrumental	53,311 (5.1)	1,012 (6.0)	2.8 ± 1.4	2.5 (1.7, 3.6)
Missing	61,278 (5.9)	1,221 (7.2)	4.1 ± 2.2	3.8 (2.2, 6.1)
Gestational age				
Over 37 weeks	945,701 (90.9)	14,664 (86.3)	3.1 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4)
32–37	65,197 (6.3)	1,637 (9.6)	2.8 ± 1.6	2.3 (1.6, 3.5)
28–32	5,700 (0.5)	204 (1.2)	2.6 ± 1.4	2.1 (1.6, 3.5)
Under 28	1,658 (0.2)	86 (0.5)	2.7 ± 1.4	2.4 (1.8, 3.6)
Missing	22,196 (2.1)	402 (2.4)	3.6 ± 1.9	3.2 (2.1, 5)
Birth weight				
2.5–4 kg	894,363 (86.0)	13,850 (81.5)	3 ± 1.7	2.6 (1.8, 4)
Under 2.5	73,724 (7.1)	1,869 (11.0)	2.8 ± 1.5	2.3 (1.6, 3.6)
Over 4	50,690 (4.9)	878 (5.2)	3.2 ± 1.7	2.8 (1.9, 4.2)
Missing	21,675 (2.1)	396 (2.3)	3.5 ± 1.8	3.1 (2.1, 4.8)
Apgar 1 minute				
8 or over	959,307 (92.2)	15,243 (89.7)	3 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 4)
Under 8	40,037 (3.8)	1,020 (6.0)	2.9 ± 1.6	2.5 (1.7, 3.8)
Missing	41,108 (4.0)	730 (4.3)	3.3 ± 1.8	2.8 (2, 4.6)
Apgar 5 minutes				
8 or over	983,719 (94.5)	15,930 (93.7)	3 ± 1.6	2.6 (1.8, 4)
Under 8	8,874 (0.9)	247 (1.5)	3.1 ± 1.8	2.6 (1.7, 4.3)
Missing	47,859 (4.6)	816 (4.8)	3.3 ± 1.8	2.8 (1.9, 4.5)

Appendix Table 1 (continued). Population characteristics by ASD status

	No ASD N (%)	ASD N (%)	Diagnosis age (years)	
			Mean ± SD	Median (IQR)
SES				
1–2	135,772 (13.0)	1,008 (5.9)	4 ± 1.9	3.8 (2.3, 5.7)
3–4	399,293 (38.4)	5,550 (32.7)	3.4 ± 1.8	3 (2, 4.7)
5–6	278,096 (26.7)	5,897 (34.7)	2.7 ± 1.5	2.3 (1.7, 3.3)
7–8	172,876 (16.6)	3,669 (21.6)	2.7 ± 1.4	2.3 (1.6, 3.4)
9–10	54,415 (5.2)	869 (5.1)	3 ± 1.5	2.6 (1.9, 3.8)
Haredi neighborhood composition				
None	635,804 (61.1)	10,591 (62.3)	2.7 ± 1.4	2.3 (1.7, 3.3)
Low	110,967 (10.7)	2,373 (14.0)	2.7 ± 1.4	2.3 (1.7, 3.2)
Medium	64,613 (6.2)	1,316 (7.7)	3.5 ± 1.8	3.1 (2, 5)
High	62,865 (6.0)	669 (3.9)	3.2 ± 1.7	2.9 (1.9, 4.2)
Very high	166,203 (16.0)	2,044 (12.0)	4.7 ± 1.7	4.8 (3.4, 6.1)

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Appendix Table 2. Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in the entire population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Intercept	1100.791***	32.434	1311.652***	31.762
Sex (Reference group: female)				
Male	-21.767*	9.514	-4.334	9.222
Population sector (Reference group: Jewish)				
Muslim Arab	12.868	22.607	31.495	21.689
Christian Arab	4.263	52.435	17.663	50.521
Druze	80.534	66.226	85.469	63.564
Muslim Bedouin	-200.216**	73.81	-140.671*	71.141
Other	19.173	19.871	36.329+	19.221
Missing	169.634***	13.544	155.030***	13.096
Maternal country of origin (Reference group: Israel)				
FSU	-89.297***	13.706	-59.998***	13.293
Ethiopia	-72.173**	24.045	-35.886	23.228
Other	-30.961	23.102	-19.59	22.344
Missing	-52.868*	21.417	-35.880+	20.677

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in the entire population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Maternal education (Reference group: academic)				
Primary	-7.959	33.961	43.186	32.802
High school	-28.423*	11.808	2.493	11.433
Tertiary education	-27.328	16.621	-12.408	16.053
Missing	-31.883*	13.017	-11.917	12.579
Maternal marital status (Reference group: married)				
Divorced	-15.562	25.726	-7.088	24.822
Single	-83.705***	16.137	-76.563***	15.569
Widow	-84.054	145.886	-5.578	140.807
Other	34.579	30.659	24.313	29.579
Missing	-70.978**	22.855	-78.483***	22.059
Maternal employment (Reference group: employed)				
Unemployed	15.998	12.383	27.250*	11.968
Student	-37.606	27.467	-34.379	26.565
Missing	45.886***	11.289	43.768***	10.899
Maternal age at birth (Reference group: 21–40-years-old)				
20 or under	164.409*	77.919	162.745*	75.191
Over 40	-21.007+	12.039	-7.143	11.625
Missing	133.237***	24.803	60.774*	24.062
Delivery type (Reference group: spontaneous)				
Cesarean section	-59.141***	10.197	-49.017***	9.853
Instrumental	-28.784+	17.497	-19.234	16.895
Missing	410.086***	18.871	410.305***	18.225
Gestational age (Reference group: over 37 weeks)				
32–37	-30.730+	16.935	5.981	16.413
28–32	-75.486+	41.452	-7.087	40.181
Less than 28	6.209	60.512	98.581+	58.6
Missing	-40.784	52.176	-63.793	50.698
Birth weight (Reference group: 2.5–4 kg)				
Under 2.5	-18.521	17.104	3.536	16.556
Over 4	2.105	18.403	-3.121	17.776
Missing	-178.340**	54.901	-182.473***	53.457
Apgar 1 minute (Reference group: 8 and over)				
Under 8	25.637	19.423	27.755	18.751
Missing	4.861	55.205	4.027	53.336

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in the entire population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Apgar 5 minutes (Reference group: 8 and over)				
Under 8	-34.914	37.251	-34.919	36.002
Missing	-48.988	50.002	-37.76	48.245
SES (Reference group: clusters 1-2)				
3-4	-46.183	27.778	-26.34	26.524
5-6	-94.161**	30.041	-85.382**	28.704
7-8	-87.364**	31.903	-99.789**	30.481
9-10	-4.012	37.377	-66.859+	35.773
Haredi neighborhood composition (Reference group: none)				
Low	-10.596	17.256	-19.9	16.45
Medium	111.920***	24.878	87.906***	23.685
High	181.741***	32.182	140.931***	30.618
Very high	603.086***	23.039	502.079***	22.188
Developmental score				
Language development			-76.149***	4.236
Social development			-46.574***	3.775
Gross motor			6.183+	3.416
Fine motor			-8.222*	3.553
SD (Intercept agas)	112.201		104.542	
SD (Observations)	518.875		500.897	
Number of observations	16,993		16,951	
R ² Marg.	0.191		0.248	
R ² Cond.	0.227		0.28	
AIC	260895.1		259016.4	
BIC	261289.9		259442	
ICC	0		0	
RMSE	511.9		494.35	

Significance levels: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Appendix Table 3. Regression models for age of ASD by sub-population

	Haredi Jews		Non-Haredi Jews		Non-Jews	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Intercept	1793.339***	63.662	909.851***	150.216	1148.824***	47.088
Sex (Reference group: female)						
Male	-77.691***	21.482	-1.163	12.755	-12.354	19.374
Maternal country of origin (Reference group: Israel)						
FSU	-187.236***	48.241	-51.268**	16.312	-174.154***	25.28
Ethiopia	-366.342***	75.353	-7.146	26.619	-104.532	66.728
Other	-103.897*	48.363	27.08	31.339	-56.685	50.225
Missing	-27.321	68.253	-108.714***	28.943	5.764	36.231
Maternal education (Reference group: academic)						
Primary	-41.12	101.257	-73.4	51.878	92.738+	51.83
High school	29.605	32.448	-49.941***	14.92	-17.128	24.006
Tertiary education	30.376	36.418	-54.343*	23.148	0.945	36.804
Missing	23.666	33.447	-55.023**	16.836	8.437	26.688
Maternal marital status (Reference group: married)						
Divorced	-210.433*	83.512	24.833	30.417	-30.112	55.938
Single	-216.735***	56.181	-74.442***	18.591	-10.877	37.191
Widow	-386.897	328.963	-5.307	178.496	55.566	382.337
Other	-29.631	145.035	57.090+	34.669	-29.65	66.551
Missing	-200.488**	71.563	-64.809*	32.585	-13.612	37.076
Maternal employment (Reference group: employed)						
Unemployed	69.288*	26.887	-5.519	17.969	-29.959	23.53
Student	11.03	61.66	-0.591	38.862	-130.211*	51.463
Missing	18.686	26.74	68.980***	14.57	39.083	24.308
Maternal age at birth (Reference group: 21–40-years-old)						
20 or under	314.960*	136.049	-39.811	130.961	205.896	149.202
Over 40	-109.939**	35.163	-0.696	14.831	-24.051	24.652
Missing	178.174*	80.322	210.291***	35.002	-42.093	42.296
Delivery type (Reference group: spontaneous)						
Cesarean section	-137.961***	30.416	-58.238***	12.819	-31.822	19.751
Instrumental	-60.776	47.665	-49.176*	21.798	28.99	36.231
Missing	501.381***	38.284	349.546***	25.744	456.807***	41.79

Appendix Table 3 (continued). Regression models for age of ASD by sub-population

	Haredi Jews		Non-Haredi Jews		Non-Jews	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Gestational age (Reference group: over 37 weeks)						
32–37	-47.865	46.968	-19.645	21.207	-51.296	34.412
28–32	-186.965	115.667	-28.697	52.298	-68.472	82.127
Less than 28	-61.924	181.613	6.312	74.607	33.42	121.8
Missing	-187.64	145.39	-29.385	68.043	16.716	98.82
Birth weight (Reference group: 2.5–4 kg)						
Under 2.5	8.832	45.913	-20.954	21.601	-16.71	34.765
Over 4	-1.866	42.335	7.955	25.718	1.564	34.547
Missing	-128.736	153.713	-113.405	72.88	-276.552**	99.87
Apgar 1 minute (Reference group: 8 and over)						
Under 8	65.597	53.821	26.099	24.429	24.875	38.978
Missing	-82.042	123.788	8.46	80.779	61.459	98.511
Apgar 5 minutes (Reference group: 8 and over)						
Under 8	-43.163	86.594	-74.496	50.023	25.691	74.657
Missing	10.496	113.676	-62.141	73.201	-49.791	88.177
SES (Reference group: cluster 1–2)						
3–4	-271.587***	60.605	88.451	150.285	67.441	44.589
5–6	-545.176***	66.626	77.47	149.781	-20.314	45.053
7–8	-534.176***	147.086	82.287	149.926	-52.949	49.548
9–10			156.704	151.295	58.212	60.39
SD (Intercept agas)	212.995		76.036		206.304	
SD (Observations)	559.813		499.267		518.532	
Number of observations	3,478		8,968		4,547	
R ² Marg.	0.179		0.048		0.061	
R ² Cond.	0.283		0.07		0.189	
AIC	53764.5		136774.6		69881.8	
BIC	54010.6		137065.8		70145.1	
ICC	0.1		0		0.1	
RMSE	546.62		494		497.37	

Significance levels: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Appendix Table 4. Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in non-Haredi population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Intercept	952.923***	36.576	1171.887***	36.208
Sex (Reference group: female)				
Male	0.212	10.766	18.654+	10.382
Maternal country of origin (Reference group: Israel)				
FSU	-64.592***	14.162	-34.755*	13.687
Ethiopia	-11.388	24.981	19.344	24.062
Other	12.297	26.875	16.271	25.824
Missing	-58.108*	23.031	-38.377+	22.143
Maternal education (Reference group: academic)				
Primary	2.25	36.924	51.592	35.527
High school	-37.731**	12.677	-2.677	12.239
Tertiary education	-48.030*	19.812	-24.704	19.054
Missing	-51.852***	14.303	-28.473*	13.775
Maternal marital status (Reference group: married)				
Divorced	11.669	26.867	11.113	25.815
Single	-65.247***	16.641	-58.192***	15.992
Widow	36.034	161.242	116.236	154.95
Other	43.686	30.707	30.831	29.507
Missing	-67.860**	24.938	-76.416**	23.969
Maternal employment (Reference group: employed)				
Unemployed	-1.25	14.19	12.629	13.651
Student	-41.456	31.006	-38.929	29.839
Missing	61.303***	12.569	59.869***	12.082
Maternal age at birth (Reference group: 21–40-years-old)				
20 and under	34.728	100.411	7.849	96.47
Over 40	-4.472	12.751	5.91	12.261
Missing	160.163***	26.687	81.076**	25.826
Delivery type (Reference group: spontaneous)				
Cesarean section	-48.544***	10.79	-43.624***	10.377
Instrumental	-25.901	18.745	-19.828	18.024
Missing	361.330***	22.376	359.251***	21.502
Gestational age (Reference group: over 37 weeks)				
32–37	-24.8	18.155	8.271	17.518
28–32	-50.072	44.406	3.989	42.862
Less than 28	17.521	63.854	97.242	61.597
Missing	-9.474	56.583	-34.908	54.608

Appendix Table 4 (continued). Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in non-Haredi population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
Birth weight (Reference group: 2.5–4 kg)				
Under 2.5	-20.104	18.473	0.955	17.815
Over 4	8.861	20.854	6.658	20.046
Missing	-170.576**	59.799	-165.282**	57.818
Apgar 1 minute (Reference group: 8 or over)				
Under 8	25.452	20.758	21.999	19.955
Missing	23.761	63.866	39.741	61.454
Apgar 5 minutes (Reference group: 8 or over)				
Under 8	-43.564	42.189	-38.034	40.622
Missing	-62.747	57.603	-65.053	55.344
SES (Reference group: cluster 1–2)				
3–4	43.751	32.708	47.7	31.608
5–6	28.981	34.352	20.929	33.181
7–8	29.987	35.212	4.16	34.018
9–10	107.065**	39.278	34.07	37.993
Population group (Reference group: Jewish)				
Muslim Arab	88.640***	21.268	102.288***	20.536
Christian Arab	80.71	51.397	92.391+	49.44
Druze	111.244+	61.933	115.778+	59.65
Muslim Bedouin	-104.702	71.529	-50.809	68.827
Other	27.61	20.15	47.524*	19.419
Missing	169.688***	14.933	154.605***	14.371
Developmental score				
Language development			-78.689***	4.789
Social development			-47.643***	4.208
Gross motor			15.993***	3.751
Fine motor			-8.566*	3.901

Appendix Table 4 (continued). Regression models for age of ASD allowance eligibility in non-Haredi population

	Model 1 (without developmental variables)		Model 2 (with developmental variables)	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
SD (Intercept agas)	74.264		72.86	
SD (Observations)	504.957		484.99	
Number of observations	12,964		12,944	
R ² Marg.	0.053		0.128	
R ² Cond.	0.073		0.147	
AIC	198089.6		196736.9	
BIC	198440.7		197117.8	
ICC	0		0	
RMSE	500.3		480.32	

Significance levels: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Source: Sarit Silverman, Guy Amit, and Yair Sadaka, Taub Center and KI Research Institute | Data: Ministry of Health; NII